

Cyber-Physical Electrical Power and Energy System Laboratory for Enabling Modern Power Systems

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Abstract—The intensive penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) poses a number of technical challenges that need to be properly addressed in order to guarantee the operation of the modern power system. With this regard, the development of new control functionalities in converter-interfaced generation to provide ancillary services is a key issue to ensure high system reliability. However, the integration of these services in field requires prior experimental validation to faithfully reproduce the behaviour of this new grid. This paper presents a comprehensive cyber-physical electrical power and energy system laboratory that integrates all elements of a modern power system, from devices to controllers, moving a step forward from power hardware in the loop. The proposed platform implements a scaled-down version of the European medium voltage distribution network proposed by CIGRE for high RES penetration. The platform performance is evaluated by testing five fundamental ancillary services: voltage control, inertial response, primary frequency control, power smoothing and harmonic compensation. Experimental results demonstrate the effectiveness and flexibility of the proposed infrastructure for testing advanced control strategies in modern power systems, bridging the gap between simulation studies and full-scale implementation.

Index Terms—Renewable energy sources, cyber-physical laboratory network, experimental validation, ancillary services, modern power systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

The energy transition towards a sustainable future affects the structure and operation of electrical power and energy systems (EPES) [1]. Over the last decades, the penetration of renewable energy sources (RES) has experienced an unprecedented growth. According to the International Energy Agency in its 2024 electricity report [2], solar photovoltaic (PV) energy is the primary driver of global electricity generation growth, meeting half of the global electricity generation increase

during 2024. Moreover, the report anticipates that RESs will account for over one-third of total electricity generation by early 2025, eclipsing coal as the primary energy source.

RES penetration causes a paradigm shift in the generation scheme and control of EPES, moving from a system composed of large generation units connected to the transmission grid and based on synchronous generators, to a system dominated by small/medium generation units based on power electronics and distributed at all grid levels. This transformation has consequences for critical aspects of EPES including control and operation of the system [3], voltage regulation [4], frequency control [5] or power quality [6], among others.

In this new era, converter-interfaced generators (CIGs) are requested to provide a range of ancillary services (AS) that allow modern EPES to operate in a robust, secure and resilient manner. These ASs, which include the provision of inertia and damping to the system [7], fast frequency response [8], primary frequency control [9], voltage control [10] or power smoothing [11], have recently been integrated into the functionalities of the CIGs, both at the generation and EPES levels. However, in order for these services to be properly deployed into the actual RES-dominated EPES with maximum guarantees, they must first be experimentally validated in laboratory environments which faithfully replicate their characteristics. These laboratory setups can provide an understanding of some physical phenomena that go unnoticed in a simulation environment, providing relevant feedback prior to pilot testing in a real system.

Reduced-scale laboratories, in terms of voltage and power, are the preferred solution for education and research activities within universities and research centers due to economic and safety reasons. In this regard, different experimental reduced-scale transmission line test beds are presented in [12]–[14] to analyse the frequency-dependent performance of this EPES component. Reduced-scale substation models have also been

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reproduced in the laboratory to address automation and protection issues in this environment [15]. Regarding microgrids, [16] describes a laboratory to analyse the mutual influence of PV inverters during islanding detection, and [17] describes a setup to analyse the interaction between two converters within a microgrid.

Distribution networks have also been reproduced in the laboratory using reduced-scale representations for different purposes. Thus, power quality impact is analysed in the laboratory described in [18] using a representation of the IEEE-13 node test feeder. A reduced-scale distribution system reproducing the European medium voltage (MV) distribution reference network proposed by CIGRE Working Group C6.04.02 has been presented in [19] by the authors, aiming to analyze the impact of RES in MV distribution networks. Furthermore, reduced-scale distribution networks are widely used to evaluate the impact of coordinated control of distributed resources [20]–[23].

This paper presents an innovative cyber-physical EPES laboratory, which is an updated version of the scaled-down distribution network developed by the authors in [19], specifically designed for the experimental validation of modern distribution grids with high penetration of RES. The main contribution of this work is to demonstrate the high flexibility of the cyber-physical EPES laboratory, which facilitates the integration of new network assets, communication infrastructures and control strategies embedded at device and control room levels. This flexibility is evaluated through the experimental demonstration of five relevant ASs: voltage control, inertial response, primary frequency control, power smoothing, and harmonic compensation. These functionalities are integrated in several CIGs of the cyber-physical EPES laboratory and their provision is coordinated by a centralised controller (CC) in order to operate the system in the most efficient way. Consequently, a secondary yet significant contribution of this paper is the experimental validation of these ASs, given that the majority of them have been evaluated exclusively in simulation environments.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section II describes in detail the updates of the cyber-physical EPES laboratory. Section III presents the fundamentals of each AS and its integration in the control structure of the laboratory. Section IV presents and analyses the experimental results obtained. Finally, Section V gathers the main conclusions of the work and future research work.

II. CYBER-PHYSICAL EPES LABORATORY

The cyber-physical EPES laboratory is based on the scaled-down network developed by the authors in [19]. This is an adapted version of the European MV distribution network proposed by the CIGRE Task Force C06.04.02 [24] for the study of RES integration. This network is composed of two distinct radial subsystems, each supplied by a primary substation connected to the transmission system, as shown in Fig. 1. The main subsystem comprises eight primary nodes (N1–N8) forming the main distribution path, with an additional

secondary branch running through nodes N9 to N11. The second subsystem represents a single branch with three nodes (N12–N14). The original MV network was scaled-down to a voltage and power rating of 400 V and 100 kVA, respectively. The electrical lines were emulated by grouping resistors and reactances, and the various consumer and generation types, including RES, were emulated by means of voltage source converters (VSCs). The control and communication system consisted of a local controller in each VSC using a digital signal processor (DSP) and a central supervision and control of the setup implemented in a real-time control platform provided by SpeedGoat. The communication between the local VSC controllers and the centralized control platform was based on the UDP/IP protocol. Further technical details of this scaled-down network can be found in [19].

This scaled-down network has recently undergone an upgrade to become a cyber-physical EPES. The objective of this upgrade is twofold: firstly, to enhance the setup flexibility through the introduction of new control capacities, instrumentation and power equipment; and secondly, to endow it with new functionalities similar to those of Power Hardware in the Loop (P-HIL) [25] and Power System Hardware in the Loop (PS-HIL) [26] testing. These enhance the flexibility and evaluation scenarios of the cyber-physical EPES laboratory. With this regard, the main updates made to the original test bed are outlined below:

- The original scaled-down network was powered exclusively from the laboratories' LV network. Currently, in addition to the LV network, it can be powered by a power amplifier capable of reproducing any voltage in a real-time simulated environment, allowing P-HIL and PS-HIL tests to be performed. As a third option, a battery energy storage system (BESS) can power the cyber-physical EPES, allowing it to operate in islanded mode.
- In the original network, the monitoring of network voltages, currents and powers was confined to those buses where a VSC was connected to. In the current implementation, power flow measurements in some branches have been added with the objective of leveraging these measurements for control room algorithms such as state estimators.
- The original VSCs were three-phase, three-wire, two-level power converters. These have now been replaced by three-phase, four-wire, two-level VSCs. This configuration increases the flexibility of the VSCs, allowing them to operate in different topologies but using a compact device. In this work, the fourth wire is used as a DC/DC converter to integrate a supercapacitor (SC) to each VSC, which provides the energy required to provide active power related ASs [27].
- The local controller of the VSCs was originally implemented by a DSP. This has been maintained, but a programmable logic controller (PLC) has also been integrated to complement the local controller, manage communication with the CC and automate all the local manoeuvres of the contactors.
- The existing communication protocol UDP/IP has been superseded by an industrial Modbus TCP/IP protocol. There-

(a) One-line diagram of the European MV distribution benchmark network proposed by CIGRE Working Group C6.04.02.

(b) Original MV scaled-down distribution network in the laboratories of the University of Sevilla.

Fig. 1: MV distribution network proposed by CIGRE Working Group C6.04.02.

Fig. 2: Communication and control infrastructure of the current cyber-physical network.

fore, all the VSC local information and measurements gathered along the network are centralized through this communication infrastructure using a protocol widely used in the EPES.

- The Speedgoat real-time control platform, which was responsible for the CC and monitoring of the original system, has been replaced by an industrial SCADA system provided by Schneider for the management and monitoring of the cyber-physical EPES laboratory. The primitive CC has evolved into a custom-made Advanced Distribution Management System (ADMS) developed on an industrial computer that commands set-points to the VSCs.
- Real-time simulators have the ability to interact with physical equipment using analog communication protocols and signals. This allows simulated real-time environments to interact with the reproduced physical system.

Fig. 2 illustrates the current communication and control infrastructure including all the devices with control functionalities. This configuration facilitates the validation of control strategies from new VSC local controllers to more sophisticated power system-level controllers, whether centralised or

distributed.

III. ANCILLARY SERVICES DESCRIPTION AND INTEGRATION

This section presents the specific controllers to be tested in the cyber-physical network for providing five fundamental ASs: voltage control, inertial response, primary frequency response (PFR), power smoothing and harmonic compensation. These controllers are developed on a hierarchical control structure composed of three levels: high-level (HL), medium-level (ML) and low-level (LL) controllers, as shown in Fig. 3. The LL control is integrated into the DSP and it corresponds to the VSC current controller [28], the SC current controller and the pulse width modulation (PWM) generation for operating the VSC IGBTs, including DC/AC and DC/DC converters [29]. In addition, this control level can also incorporate resonant controllers to provide harmonic compensation [30]. The LL controller runs in regular time intervals in the order of micro- and nano-seconds for the current controllers and PWM respectively. The ML controller is in charge of providing the current references to the LL controller $i_{s,dq}^*$ and i_{SC}^* . For this purpose, this control layer considers the active and reactive power references p^* and q^* coming from the HL controller which are modified depending on the implemented ASs, as shown in Fig. 3. The ML is executed in regular but larger time intervals ranging from milliseconds to tens of milliseconds, being possible, therefore, to integrate it either in the DSP or the PLC. Finally, the HL control layer is responsible for running quasi-steady state algorithms to generating the power references to the ML controller and parametrizing the AS control gains of each individual VSC to optimize the overall performance of the distribution system. This control layer is integrated into the industrial PC and it is run in regular intervals in the order of seconds or minutes.

The following subsections detail the fundamentals and specific controllers of each of the ASs that have been tested into

Fig. 3: Hierarchical control structure and ancillary services integration in the cyber-physical EPES laboratory.

the cyber-physical EPES laboratory. It should be noted that these controllers are those currently implemented but this does not prevent the use of other alternative control strategies.

A. Inertial Response

The deployment of this AS is intended to occur at both the VSC and grid levels. At the VSC level, inertia provision is developed by operating the VSCs in grid-forming mode. Specifically, the type of grid-forming control implemented is the synchronverter presented in [31], which was experimentally validated in [32]. This grid-forming control consists of an active and reactive power loop based on a PI controller implemented in the ML layer that provides reference currents through a virtual admittance to the LL control. The active power loop is responsible for synchronising the VSC with the grid by generating the virtual angular velocity θ_v of the grid-forming VSC. One of the main features of this type of grid-forming controller is the ability to separate the inertial response from the PFR. In this way, it is possible to provide only the inertial response, the PFR or both, leading to a greater flexibility compared to grid-forming controllers based on the swing equation [33]. The required additional power injected/absorbed for providing the inertial response is supplied by the SC connected to the DC bus of the VSC [32]. The control of the DC bus voltage is within the ML layer, as well as the corresponding SC energy management system. The current loop, on the other hand, is within the LL layer. The reactive power loop provides the virtual electromotive force of the grid-forming controller which defines the VSC voltage amplitude. The implementation of the synchronverter, together with the current control and the PWM, forms the basic structure of the VSC control. The rest of the ASs are added to this structure being described in the following subsections.

On the other hand, at the grid level, RESs connected to the MV distribution network can assist in maintaining system frequency through inertial response. To this end, Transmission System Operator (TSO) may request a certain inertial response

from the RESs within distribution networks in the primary substation, i.e. border between the transmission and distribution levels. To satisfy this TSO requirement, the Distribution System Operator (DSO) may run an optimization algorithm in the HL layer that computes the individual virtual inertial response H_i of each RES minimizing the network power losses and satisfying the network technical constraints. The optimisation algorithm is composed of two stages. Firstly, the maximum increment of active power injection at the primary substation due to the contribution of the SCs within the RES is determined. This increase in power is associated with a certain maximum value of aggregated inertia, H_{ag}^{max} , that the distribution network can supply to the transmission system for a specific value of rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) and a base power of the distribution network S_{base}^{sys} . Subsequent to the attainment of this result, the TSO demands a feasible H_{ag} at the point of interconnection (POI) to the DSO. Consequently, a second optimization algorithm is executed in order to assign an individual H_i to each RES. This second algorithm guarantees the required H_{ag} at the POI and minimises the active power losses within the distribution system. A comprehensive exposition of the optimization algorithm can be found in [34].

B. Voltage Control

The tested voltage control strategy of the MV network in the presence of RES is based on the voltage control algorithm presented in [35]. The experimental validation of this proposal in the scaled-down network was successfully carried out in [36].

C. Primary Frequency Response

The PFR is implemented in the ML and HL control layers. In the ML control, a $f(P)$ droop curve is implemented to adjust the RES active power reference based on the grid frequency [37]. This curve contains a normal operating zone, where the PFR service is not activated, when the frequency is close to the rated frequency within a predetermined dead band Δf_n . Outside this band, under/over-frequency events can occur, which are mitigated in each RES by a classic droop controller for under/over-frequency events.

Similar to the inertial response, an optimisation algorithm is implemented in the HL controller that determines the $f(P)$ curves of each RES. The specific optimisation algorithm has been presented and validated by simulation in [37].

D. High/Low-Frequency Power Smoothing

The objective of this service is to ensure RES active power injections to the PCC with minimum variations despite abrupt variations of the primary energy source due to clouds covering part of a PV plant or a gust of wind in a wind park. This intermittent power can cause unwanted voltage rises and flicker in distribution networks, thus reducing the power quality of the final users. In particular, high frequency power smoothing (HFPS) aims to mitigate fast intermittences that cause an abrupt power variation from the RES with a short duration

of the order of seconds. The integration of this service is implemented in the ML controller and the algorithm proposed at the RES level is presented and experimentally validated in [38]. It is based on a ramp-rate limiter that mitigates high-frequency fluctuations using the energy of the SC within the DC bus of the VSC. The enhancement achieved by equipping each RES with the HFPS capacity to mitigate rapid voltage fluctuations on the cyber-physical EPES laboratory has been evaluated in [39].

The RES volatility can also cause frequency variations and for this reason, many TSOs require specific ramp-rate limits (RRL) at the POI primary substations between transmission and distribution networks. To comply with this TSO-imposed RRL, the integration of a central BESS close to the primary substation is proposed to limit the ramp rates [40]. This functionality is named Low-Frequency Power Smoothing (LFPS).

E. Harmonic Compensation

The harmonic compensation functionality is integrated at the VSC in the LL controller. This consists of a voltage control loop cascaded with a current control loop. Both voltage and current control are based on resonant controllers tuned to the harmonic frequencies to be compensated and integrated in parallel with the main VSC current control loop. It also has an algorithm that limits the VSC harmonic filtering capacity in the event of an VSC overload due to the activation of this service. The tuning of the resonant controllers, the overload limitation algorithm and the experimental validation at VSC level were explored in [30].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the experimental results corresponding to the evaluation of the ASs described in the previous section on the cyber-physical EPES laboratory. In particular, the tests are carried out in subsystem 1 of the scaled-down network with two VSCs operating as loads (nodes N5, N8) and three CIGs which can provide the previous ASs (nodes N6, N9 and N11). The VSCs representing loads operate as grid-following converters, tracking a given active and reactive power reference.

The ASs corresponding to voltage control and HFPS have already been evaluated into the cyber-physical network in works [36] and [38], [39] respectively. Therefore, the experimental results of these ASs are not included in this paper.

A. Inertial Response

The objective of this study is to evaluate the inertial response capability from RES connected to the distribution network to the transmission network in the event of a frequency disturbance. In this test, the PFR functionality of the CIGs is deactivated. For the purposes of this study, the cyber-physical EPES laboratory is supplied by the power amplifier to generate a frequency events with a constant 0.5 Hz/s RoCoF, as shown in Fig. 4. In this way, the controller's performance is evaluated under both under- and over-frequency conditions, as well as for positive and negative RoCoFs, covering a wide range of

Fig. 4: Frequency perturbation applied to the POI for evaluating the inertia response, the PFR and the combined action of both.

possible scenarios. The load at nodes N5 and N8 is 5 kW/1.6 kvar and 3.7 kW/0.75 respectively while the CIGs are injecting a maximum of 10 kW with unity power factor, half of its rated power $S_{rat}^{CIG} = 20$ kVA. Consequently, it is represented an scenario where the distribution system is exporting power to the transmission one.

Considering this scenario, the capability of the distribution network to provide inertial response is evaluated by executing the optimization algorithm described in subsection III-A. The first part of the algorithm yields a maximum aggregated power of 7.39 kW that corresponds to a maximum POI aggregated inertia constant $H_{ag}^{max} = 6.16$ s, considering a RoCoF of 0.50 Hz/s and a base power of $S_{base}^{sys} = 60$ kVA (3 CIGs of 20 kVA). Then, it is assumed that the TSO request these maximum POI aggregated inertia $H_{ag} = H_{ag}^{max} = 6.16$ s. As a result, the second optimization algorithm of the methodology assigns an identical virtual inertia constant to each CIG, $H_i = 6.66$ s, that guarantees the required POI H_{ag} with the minimum power losses.

Fig. 5a shows the POI active power during the test where it can be clearly noticed the fast inertial response actuation due to the frequency excursions shown in Fig. 4. As expected, the first and third frequency events (50 Hz to 48 Hz and 52 Hz to 50 Hz) lead to an increase of power at the POI while during the second and fourth frequency changes (48 Hz to 50 Hz and 50 Hz to 52 Hz) the performance is just the opposite. It is noteworthy that the observed power increase is approximately 7.2 kW, which is in close agreement with the theoretical value derived from the selected inertial constant at the POI: $2H_{ag} \cdot RoCoF \cdot S_{base} = 2 \cdot 6.16 \cdot 0.5 / 50 \cdot 60 = 7.39$ kW. In addition, note that the power remains almost constant when the RoCoF is null, with only minor deviations attributable to the active power absorption of the CIGs, required to ensure the secure state of charge of SC within the CIGs, deviating from its reference value.

The aggregated active power injected at the POI is given by each CIG connected at the distribution network as represented in Fig. 5b. The individual CIG active power injection for the inertial response is about 2.5 kW which corresponds to the theoretical value: $2 \cdot H_i \cdot RoCoF \cdot S_{base}^{CIG} = 2 \cdot 6.66 \cdot 0.5 / 50 \cdot 20 = 2.6$ kW. The effect of the SC is also evident in the injected CIG active power, since the theoretical inertial response is not fully

(a) Active and reactive power injected at POI

(b) Active and reactive power injected by each CIG

Fig. 5: Experimental results of the inertial response.

achieved, in part due to the power being required to guarantee a safe state of charge of the SC.

It is also important to note that during the inertial response, the reactive power disturbance in the CIGs is minimal, remaining close to zero. This is in contrast to the POI reactive power as shown in Fig. 5a. The reason is that the inertial response provided by the CIGs leads to a variation in the power flows of the network branches and therefore to a variation in active and reactive power losses.

B. Inertia and Primary Frequency Response

This section evaluates the combined action of inertial response and PFR in the cyber-physical EPES laboratory. The virtual inertia constant and PFR droop for each CIG are computed following the same methodology explained in the previous section for each AS. The frequency events applied at the POI exhibit a similar pattern to that depicted in Fig. 4.

The test results, shown in Fig. 6a, clearly demonstrate the combined action of both responses at the POI. The inertial response acts with a time constant of about 100 ms, while the PFR operates with 1 s. During the first event (50 Hz - 48 Hz, $t=200$ s), an initial fast reaction corresponding to the inertial response is observed, followed by a progressive power increase due to the PFR. This effect can be clearly appreciated in the rest of events. Fig. 6b shows the individual contribution of each CIG. Notably, the CIG connected to bus N6 contributes

(a) Active and reactive power injection at the POI during the test.

(b) Active power injection of POI during the test.

Fig. 6: Experimental results of the combined action of inertial response and PFR.

the most to PFR, as its operation for this AS leads to minimal distribution network power losses. This requires the CIG to operate with the largest headroom, which explains why its injected power follows an opposite trend to those connected to buses N9 and N11.

The results demonstrate that the combined implementation of inertial response and PFR enables effective system frequency regulation. The inertial response provides an immediate reaction to disturbances, while the PFR ensures sustained active power adjustment to maintain system balance.

C. Low-Frequency Power Smoothing

The LFPS evaluation is performed by connecting an additional VSC to the bus N1 of the scaled-down network, which emulates a BESS equipped with this functionality. Conversely, the HFPS functionality of the CIGs is deactivated. Therefore, the impact of the LFPS ramp-rate limitation is predominantly discernible in the active power injected into the upstream grid.

This phenomenon is evidenced in Fig. 7. The red line shows the POI active power of a distribution network with PV plants on cloudy days [38] without LFPS algorithm implementation. Significant variations in the POI power are observed during brief periods, even resulting in a change in the direction of the power flow between the transmission and distribution grids. For instance, between $t=100$ s and $t=150$ s, the active power

Fig. 7: Active power injections at the POI without and with LFPS.

oscillates from 10 kW to 8 kW, with a reverse power flow between these two values. The activation of the LFPS with a ramp limitation of 166 W/s in the BESS mitigates these power fluctuations, as can be observed in the green line. For the same time period, the power oscillates between 10 kW and 6 kW, avoiding the reverse power flow and a minimum power of 2 kW.

D. Harmonic Compensation

This subsection describes the active harmonic compensation in the cyber-physical EPES laboratory. This is achieved by replacing the existing loads at nodes N5 and N8 with non-linear loads consisting of three-phase diode bridges supplying a resistive load. The resistors connected to the diode bridges of N5 and N8 have a value of 50 Ω and 100 Ω respectively. This configuration allows the presence of $6k \pm 1$ harmonics circulating through the network. In addition, the power amplifier connected to the POI injects a harmonic voltage of 10V for the 5th harmonic and 5V for the 7th harmonic.

The control algorithm implemented in the CIGs aims to completely eliminate harmonic voltage corresponding to 5th and 7th harmonics at their respective PCC as explained in subsection III-E. Fig. 8 compares the harmonic spectrum of the voltage at N11 in the case of the CIG active harmonic filtering (AHF) capability is activated or not. As can be seen, the 5th and 7th harmonic content are significant, exceeding 6% and 4% respectively when the AHF is disabled. This results in a total harmonic distortion (THD) of 7.81%. The activation of the AHF functionality significantly reduces the presence of the 5th and 7th harmonics, although it does not completely eliminate them. In addition, there is an excitation of the 11th and 13th harmonics with respect to the previous case. Despite the increase in these harmonics, the large reduction in the 5th and 7th harmonics reduces the THD at node N11 to 3.16%.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a versatile cyber-physical EPES laboratory that closely mimics the performance of modern active distribution networks with a massive RES penetration,

Fig. 8: Harmonic spectrum of voltages at node N11 under harmonic distortion and nonlinear loads without and with the activation of the AHF functionality.

while providing the flexibility and controllability required for advanced research and validation of innovative control strategies. The combination of high-performance physical components with sophisticated cyber infrastructure allows any type of control algorithm and device to be tested under realistic conditions, making it an invaluable tool for the development and validation of next generation smart grid technologies.

In order to assess the reliability of these infrastructure, five ancillary services for RES-dominated systems have been evaluated: voltage regulation, inertial response, PFR, power smoothing and harmonic compensation. These services have been integrated into the control and communication infrastructure of the cyber-physical EPES laboratory, which follows the structure of a real power system. In this current work, experimental results have been presented for inertial response, PFR and both combined, LFPS and harmonic compensation. The algorithms enabling these services have been previously proposed and validated in simulation, and their experimental validation in the cyber-physical EPES laboratory is a step forward for their implementation in real power systems.

Future research on the cyber-physical EPES laboratory will focus on providing new control devices, such as the integration of an electronic on-load tap-changers or μ PMUs for monitoring and control purposes. In addition, new network topologies such as hybrid AC/DC networks or three-phase four-wire systems will be considered. In terms of system control, distributed control strategies will be considered as alternatives to centralised ones, as well as the use of artificial intelligence techniques for controlling and monitoring related activities. Moreover, the availability of the cyber part of the laboratory, including a realistic OT infrastructure, unlocks the possibility of analysing the cybersecurity issues in the context of modern EPES.

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